

Assessment of the Relationship between Hygiene Practices and Water contamination levels of waters used by Restaurants and Local food vendors in Aba, Abia State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT:

Safe and clean water continues to be one of the most critical issues of public health, especially in developing nations where water pollution is rampant. This research evaluated the connection between hygiene practices and water contamination of water samples collected from restaurants and food vendors in Aba City, Abia State, Nigeria. A total of 120 water samples obtained from various sources, including borehole, rainwater, municipal supply, itinerant vendors, sachet water, and bottled water were analyzed using standard laboratory methods to detect the parasitic and microbial contaminants of water. The results revealed that 27 (22.5%) of the samples were contaminated with parasites while 47 (39.2%) were contaminated with microorganisms. Parasitological examination identified 9 samples each contaminated with *Ascaris lumbricoides*, *Giardia lamblia*, and *Cryptosporidium* oocysts. Microbiological analysis showed that 22 samples contained total coliforms, 11 had *Escherichia coli*, 7 had *Salmonella* spp., and 7 had *Staphylococcus aureus*. Contamination was observed in both drinking water (15 parasitic; 23 microbial) and water used for food preparation (12 parasitic; 24 microbial), indicating multiple exposure pathways. Assessment based on water sources showed that borehole and municipal water recorded the highest contamination levels, while sachet and bottled water had comparatively lower but still notable contamination. The findings highlight widespread contamination across all water sources and demonstrate a clear association between poor hygiene practices and increased water contamination. There is need for improved water treatment, regular monitoring, and enhanced hygiene education to reduce the risk of waterborne diseases and ensure public health safety.

Keywords: Hygiene practices, Water contamination, Restaurants, Local food vendors, Aba

INTRODUCTION:

The significance of water and food in relation to human survival can never be understated. Restaurants have become part of the food distribution system within many poor countries including Nigeria. The restaurants produce ready-made food products which are sold in open places and observe varying levels of safety and hygiene standards. Surface water, dug wells, borehole, and piped water system linked to a standpipe are some of the sources of water which are commonly employed by the vendors (Kristanti et.al., 2020). Some of the restaurants would also make use of well-water to cook their food products. Nevertheless, it is not known if the water would first be treated. The quality of such water must be up to standard

for human consumption. Water quality problems and massive contamination remain unsolved leading to transmission of various water-borne diseases. Protozoan pathogens associated with water contamination include *Acanthamoeba* spp, *Entamoeba histolytica*, *Cryptosporidium*, *Balantidium coli*, *Blastocystis* spp, *Cyclospora cayetanensis*, *Giardia* spp, *Isoospora belli*, *Microsporidia*, *Naegleria fowleri* and *Toxoplasma gondi* (WHO, 2022). The control of the water-borne transmission presents real challenges, because a substantial number of pathogens produce cysts, oocysts or eggs that are extremely resistant to processes generally engaged in the disinfection of water sources and in certain

instances can be difficult to remove by filtration processes.

Aba, Abia State, is a rapidly expanding commercial city characterized by a high density of informal food vending activities. Due to inconsistent municipal water supply and infrastructural limitations, many food establishments rely on alternative water sources such as boreholes, water vendors, and stored tank water. These sources may not undergo adequate treatment or routine quality monitoring. Despite the potential risks, there is limited documented evidence regarding the hygiene practices and microbiological and parasitological quality of water used by restaurants and local food vendors in Aba. This study is of great public health, regulatory, academic, and socio-economic importance. Water plays a fundamental role in food preparation, utensil washing, environmental sanitation, and personal hygiene within food establishments. In a densely populated and commercially active city such as Aba, where restaurants and informal food vending businesses are widespread and heavily patronized, the microbiological and parasitological safety of water used in food handling becomes a critical issue. Contaminated water can serve as a major vehicle for the transmission of pathogenic microorganisms and parasites responsible for waterborne and foodborne diseases such as cholera, typhoid fever, dysentery, and gastroenteritis. Therefore, assessing the hygienic conditions under which water is stored and used, alongside laboratory evaluation of its microbial and parasitic quality is essential for safeguarding public health. The findings of this study will provide empirical and laboratory-based evidence on the safety status of water used in restaurants and by local food vendors in Aba. By identifying microbial contaminants such as coliform bacteria and other pathogenic organisms, as well as parasitic forms including cysts and ova, the study will establish whether the water sources comply with acceptable public health standards. This evidence will help determine the level of exposure risk faced by consumers who patronize these food establishments. In doing so, the research will contribute significantly to efforts aimed at reducing the incidence of waterborne and foodborne diseases within the city and its surrounding communities.

Furthermore, the study will be valuable to regulatory and environmental health authorities responsible for

monitoring hygiene practices in food establishments. Agencies operating within Abia State require reliable local data to design and implement effective monitoring and enforcement strategies. The results of this research will provide baseline information that can guide inspections, inform policy adjustments, and support the development of evidence-based public health interventions. Rather than relying solely on routine inspections, regulatory bodies will be equipped with scientific findings that can strengthen compliance enforcement and improve food safety governance. More so, the socio-economic relevance of the study cannot be overlooked. Aba is a major commercial hub with high population mobility and significant patronage of ready-to-eat foods. Any outbreak of waterborne or foodborne disease linked to contaminated water in food establishments could have serious health and economic consequences. By providing data that supports preventive measures, this study contributes to the protection of public health, reduction of healthcare burdens, and promotion of sustainable food safety practices. Overall, the research is timely, relevant, and necessary for improving hygiene standards and ensuring the safety of water used in food establishments in Aba.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Descriptions of the Study Area:

This study was conducted in Aba, the commercial hub of Abia State, Nigeria. Aba town of Abia State, located in the South East geopolitical zone of Nigeria, lies within longitude 5° 7' 0.00"N and latitude 7° 22' 0.00"E. Aba hosts a large population, estimated at over 2 million, with dense markets, informal settlements, and diverse economic activities. Its climate is tropical, with a rainy season between April and October, which influences water quality via runoff and potential fecal contamination (Ogbuagu *et al.*, 2019). Water sources in Aba include municipal pipe-borne water, boreholes, wells, and water supplied by private vendors. The selection of Aba as the study site is due to its high concentration of food establishments and limited documented information on water quality and hygiene practices in these sectors.

Figure 1: Map of Abia State showing the sampling locations (Source: Google Map)

Ethical Considerations:

Ethical approval was obtained from Abia State Ministry of Health and Imo State University Ethical Review Committee. Written consent was obtained from restaurant owners and food vendors. Data confidentiality and anonymity were maintained.

Hygiene Assessment:

Hygiene practices in the sampled food establishments were evaluated using a structured observational checklist and a questionnaire. The assessment focused on critical parameters including the hand-washing practices of food handlers, the sanitation of utensils and food preparation surfaces, methods of water storage such as whether containers were covered or uncovered and the types of containers used, the frequency and type of water treatment applied including boiling, chlorination, or filtration and the level of knowledge food handlers possessed regarding safe water handling. The checklist and questionnaire were adopted from established food safety guidelines provided by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2022) and the

Codex Alimentarius Commission (2020) to ensure alignment with internationally recognized standards for food hygiene and water safety. This approach allowed for a comprehensive evaluation of hygiene practices that could influence the microbiological and parasitological quality of water used in food preparation.

Sample Size Determination:

In this work, the formula of Nwana 1981 was adopted. Nwana in his work on educational research observe that “if the population is a few hundred, 40% or more sample will do; if many hundreds a 20% sample will do; if a few thousand 10% sample will do and if several thousand a 5% or less will do”.In the present work, there are 300 restaurants and feeding centers in Aba, Abia State and by Nwana 1981, the sample size for the present work is going to be 20 of 300, which 60.

Study Population:

The population of this study comprised of restaurant and local food vendors involved in food preparation and sales

within Aba metropolis. A total of 60 sampling sites were selected from the three L.G.A of Aba (Aba South, Aba North and Osisioma). The target population included both registered and unregistered food establishments operating within Aba metropolis. These establishments vary in size and structure, ranging from small roadside food stalls and informal local vendors to larger, formal sit-down restaurants. Individuals considered part of the population included food handlers, water handlers, and managerial or supervisory staff responsible for food preparation and hygiene practices within these establishments. Including these categories of personnel allowed the study to capture a comprehensive view of water use practices, sanitation conditions, and hygiene management within the food vending sector. This approach ensured that the study population adequately represented the diversity of food service operations present within Aba metropolis and provided relevant insights into the potential public health risks associated with water use in food preparation environments.

Water Sample Collection:

Each vendor provided two water samples:

- A. Drinking water
- B. Water used for food preparation

A total 120 water samples were collected from all the sampling sites and location. Samples were collected in 1000 ml polyethylene bottles for parasitological analyses and in 500 ml sterile bottles for microbiological parameters. Samples from sachet and bottled water were agitated and carefully transferred into sampling bottles. Immediately after collection, the cap and cover were carefully replaced. All sampling bottles were not filled up to the brim, a 20-30 mm space were left for effective shaking of the bottle (APHA, 2017). Sample bottles were accurately identified with a number code; date and time of collection, site of collection, and source of water. Samples were conveyed to the laboratory within three hours of collection in a light-proof insulated cold box containing ice packs. Analysis of water samples began immediately following sampling to avoid unpredictable changes in the microbial population (Gaudy 1998). All samples were conveyed to the laboratory, Department of Science Laboratory Technology, Ogbonnaya Onu Polytechnic, Aba, within three hours of collection in a light-proof insulated cold box containing ice packs and immediately stored at 4°C.

Processing of Water Samples for Parasitological Analysis:

For purpose of microscopy, concentration by centrifuge as described by (WHO 2017) was adopted. Thus: A filter paper was placed into a funnel and then place on top of a centrifuge tube; the water samples in each container were

shook and passed through the filter into separate tubes to reach the 10ml mark. The filter was then removed and particulate materials present was discarded. Samples were centrifuged for 5 minutes at a predetermined speed of $100 \times g$ (300rpm) to concentrate the parasites. After the period of centrifuge, the supernatant was discarded by gently inverting the tubes leaving the deposits in the tube. A drop of the deposits was placed on a clean slide for examination under a microscope.

Statistical Analysis:

Data were analyzed using frequencies, percentages, and Chi-square test to determine associations between hygiene practices and water contamination. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Laboratory Analysis:

Identification of Parasites

Parasites were identified by the morphological structures of their cysts, ova or larvae when focus under the microscope Cheesbrough (2000) with the aid of the following procedures:

Direct Wet Preparation of Water Samples:

Using a Pasteur pipette, the deposit was placed on a clean grease-free glass slide and covered with cover slip to avoid air bubbles and over floating. The sample was viewed microscopically using x10 and x40 objective for focusing and identification of parasites, respectively.

Iodine Preparation of Water Samples:

A drop of Lugol's iodine was placed at the edge of the slide. The smear was examined systematically under the microscope using x10 and x40 objectives for focusing and identification of parasites, respectively (Subashini *et.al.*, 2014).

Microbiological Analysis:

Microbiological analysis was done according to the method described by (Cheesbrough, 2000). The media used were prepared according to the manufacturer's instruction stated on the media. The glass wares such as Petri dishes, conical flasks, test tubes, beakers and bijou bottles were thoroughly washed and sterilized in a hot air oven at 160°C for an hour. The inoculating loop was sterilized by flaming in the Bunsen burner until it turns red hot. Similarly, microbial load on the working surfaces were reduced by the application of disinfectant solution (70% ethanol).

Determination of total bacterial count:

The water samples collected from all the sampling locations and sites were homogenized by shaking them for 25 times, beside a Bunsen burner. The bacterial load

of the water samples were determined by performing ten-fold serial dilution in test tubes containing peptone water up to 10^{-5} . Nine milliliters (9mls) of peptone water was transferred aseptically into 5 sterile test tubes labeled 10^{-1} to 10^{-5} , one ml of the water samples were also aseptically transferred into the first tube (10^{-1}) with a sterile pipette then serial dilution. This was repeated until the 5th tube. The total viable count (Total plate count) was determined using the pour plate technique, cultured in triplicates. 1ml of the samples from 10^{-1} to 10^{-3} of the dilution test tubes were aseptically transferred into the Petri plates. The plates were labeled before inoculation and the culture medium was Nutrient Agar. The medium was prepared according to the manufacturer's instruction and sterilized by autoclaving at 121°C for 15 minutes at 15psi and then allowed to cool to 45°C before dispensing about twenty milliliters into sterile Petri dishes and allowed to solidify, inverted to prevent condensation droppings from the lid into the agar and incubated in the incubator at 37°C for 24 hours. A control was equally prepared without adding the sample. The bacterial colonies ranging from 30 to 300 were counted and expressed in colony forming unit per ml (CFU/ml). The bacteria isolates were counted using a colony counter and sub-cultured on a freshly prepared nutrient agar for characterization and identification.

Data Analysis:

Data from the field surveys and laboratory results were analyzed using simple frequencies and percentages for hygiene practices, water source types, and contamination levels. While Chi-square test was used to determine the associations between hygiene practices and water contamination.

RESULTS:

Table 1 shows the parasitological quality of water samples. A total of 120 water samples were analyzed, comprising 60 drinking water samples (50.0%) and 60 preparation water samples (50.0%). Overall, 27 samples were positive, giving a prevalence of 22.50% (27/120), while 93 samples (77.50%) were negative. Each parasite *Ascaris lumbricoides*, *Giardia lamblia*, and *Cryptosporidium* oocysts—was detected in 9 samples each, representing 7.50% (9/120) respectively. For drinking water, 15 samples were positive (25.00%), while 45 (75.00%) were negative. For preparation water, 12 samples were positive (20.00%), while 48 (80.00%) were negative. A chi-square test comparing contamination between drinking water and preparation water showed that there was no statistically significant difference between the two groups ($p > 0.05$). Also, there was no statistically significant association between water type and parasitological contamination ($\chi^2 = 0.40$, $df = 1$, $p > 0.05$). Table 2 shows the microbiological quality of water samples. A total of 120 water samples were analyzed,

comprising 60 drinking water samples (50.0%) and 60 preparation water samples (50.0%). Out of the total samples, 47 were positive for microbiological contamination, giving an overall prevalence of 39.17% (47/120), while 73 samples (60.83%) were negative. Total coliforms were detected in 22 samples (18.33%; 22/120), *Escherichia coli* in 11 samples (9.17%; 11/120), *Salmonella* spp. in 7 samples (5.83%; 7/120), and *Staphylococcus aureus* in 7 samples (5.83%; 7/120). For drinking water, 23 out of 60 samples were positive (0.383; 38.33%), while 37 samples (0.617; 61.67%) were negative. For preparation water, 24 out of 60 samples were positive (0.40; 40.00%), while 36 samples (0.60; 60.00%) were negative. Chi-square analysis revealed no statistically significant difference in microbiological contamination between drinking water and preparation water samples ($p > 0.05$). Also, the microbiological contamination ($\chi^2 = 0.04$, $df = 1$, $p > 0.05$), was independent of water type. Table 3 illustrates the water sources vs contamination levels. A total of 120 water samples were analyzed. Out of these, 74 samples were contaminated, representing a prevalence of 61.67%. Borehole water accounted for 19 contaminated samples (15.83%). Municipal water also recorded 19 contaminated samples (15.83%). Itinerant water supply contributed 16 contaminated samples (13.33%). Rainwater and sachet water each recorded 7 contaminated samples (5.83%), while bottled water had 6 contaminated samples (5.00%). Parasitic contamination accounted for 27/120 (22.50%), while microbiological contamination accounted for 47/120 (39.17%). There is no statistically significant association between water source and type of contamination ($p > 0.05$) and there was no statistically significant association between water source and type of contamination ($p > 0.05$). A total of 120 water samples were analyzed across three hygiene categories. The overall contamination prevalence was 61.67% (74/120). The contamination rate among samples obtained from vendors with good hygiene practices was 46.67% (14/30). For vendors with moderate hygiene, the contamination rate was 60.00% (24/40), while vendors with poor hygiene practices had a contamination rate of 72.00% (36/50). The corresponding proportions were 0.467, 0.600, and 0.720 for good, moderate, and poor hygiene levels, respectively. Relative risk analysis showed that samples from vendors with moderate hygiene had a 1.29 times higher contamination risk, while those from vendors with poor hygiene had a 1.54 times higher risk, compared to those with good hygiene. The absolute increase in contamination risk was 13.3% for moderate hygiene and 25.3% for poor hygiene relative to good hygiene. A chi-square test demonstrated a statistically significant association between hygiene level and contamination status ($\chi^2 = 6.87$, $df = 2$, $p < 0.05$).

Table 1: Parasitological Quality of Water Samples (n = 120)

Parasite Identified	Drinking Water (n=60)	Preparation Water (n=60)	Total Positive (n=120)	Prevalence (%)
<i>Ascaris lumbricoides</i>	6	3	9	7.50
<i>Giardia lamblia</i>	5	4	9	7.50
<i>Cryptosporidium</i> oocysts	4	5	9	7.50
Total Positive Samples	15	12	27	22.50

Table 2: Microbiological Quality of Water Samples (n = 120)

Parameter	Drinking Water (n=60)	Preparation Water (n=60)	Total Positive (n=120)	Prevalence (%)
Total coliforms	10	12	22	18.33
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	6	5	11	9.17
<i>Salmonella</i> spp.	4	3	7	5.83
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	3	4	7	5.83
Total Positive Samples	23	24	47	39.17

Table 3: Water Sources vs Contamination Levels (n = 120)

Water Source	Parasitic Contamination	Microbiological Contamination	Total Contaminated Samples	Prevalence (%)
Borehole	7	12	19	15.83
Rainwater	2	5	7	5.83
Municipal water	7	12	19	15.83
Itinerant water supply	6	10	16	13.33
Sachet water	3	4	7	5.83
Bottled water	2	4	6	5.00
Total	27	47	74	61.67

Table 4: Hygiene Practices and Contamination of Water Samples (n = 120)

Hygiene Level	No. of Vendors	Samples Examined	Contaminated Samples	Contamination Rate (%)	Proportion (p)
Good	15	30	14	46.67	0.467
Moderate	20	40	24	60.00	0.600
Poor	25	50	36	72.00	0.720
Total	60	120	74	61.67	0.617

Statistical Association:

A statistically significant association was observed between hygiene practices and water contamination levels ($\chi^2 = 6.87$, df = 2, $p < 0.05$). Vendors with poor hygiene practices demonstrated significantly higher contamination rates compared to those with good hygiene practices.

DISCUSSION:

The parasitological assessment of the 120 water samples revealed the presence of important intestinal parasites of public health importance. Out of the 120 water samples analyzed, 9 samples (7.5%) were contaminated with *Ascaris lumbricoides*, 9 samples (7.5%) with *Giardia lamblia*, and 9 samples (7.5%) with *Cryptosporidium* oocysts. Overall, 27 samples were contaminated with parasites, of which 15 were drinking water samples and 12 were water used for food preparation. These findings indicate that both direct consumption and indirect

exposure through food handling constitute significant pathways for parasitic infections. The detection of *Ascaris lumbricoides* in 9 samples suggests contamination from human or animal faecal matter, as the eggs of this helminth are commonly transmitted through soil and water contaminated with faeces. *A. lumbricoides* is one of the most prevalent soil-transmitted helminths globally and is strongly associated with poor sanitation and hygiene conditions (WHO, 2022). The presence of its eggs in water samples is particularly concerning because they are highly resistant to environmental conditions and

can remain viable for long periods, thereby increasing the risk of transmission through contaminated water (WHO, 2022; Bulus *et.al.*, 2024). Similarly, the occurrence of *Giardia lamblia* in 9 samples highlights the risk of protozoan infections associated with contaminated water sources. *G. lamblia* is a flagellated protozoan parasite that causes giardiasis, a common cause of diarrheal disease worldwide. It is frequently transmitted through ingestion of cysts in contaminated water and is known for its resistance to conventional water treatment methods such as chlorination (Bulus *et.al.*, 2024). The detection of *Giardia* cysts in both drinking and food preparation water suggests inadequate water treatment or post-treatment contamination, consistent with previous studies in developing regions. The identification of *Cryptosporidium* oocysts in 9 samples further emphasizes the public health implications of the findings. *Cryptosporidium* is a significant waterborne pathogen responsible for cryptosporidiosis, a disease characterized by diarrhea that can be severe in immunocompromised individuals. The oocysts are highly resistant to environmental stress and disinfection processes, allowing them to persist in water supplies even after treatment (WHO, 2022). Their presence in water used for both drinking and food preparation is therefore a major concern. Overall, the equal distribution of the three parasites (*Ascaris lumbricoides*, *Giardia lamblia*, and *Cryptosporidium* oocysts) suggests widespread environmental contamination and highlights the need for improved water sanitation and hygiene practices. The findings align with global reports indicating that parasitic contamination of water remains a major public health issue in developing countries, where access to safe drinking water and proper sanitation is limited (WHO, 2022).

The microbiological analysis of the water samples revealed significant levels of bacterial contamination, indicating potential public health concerns. Of the samples examined, 22(18.3%) were contaminated with total coliforms, 11(9.2%) with *Escherichia coli*, 7(5.8%) with *Salmonella* spp., and 7(5.8%) with *Staphylococcus aureus*. A total of 47 samples were contaminated overall, with 23 originating from drinking water sources and 24 from water used for food preparation. The presence of total coliforms in 22 samples suggests general microbial contamination and possible deficiencies in water treatment, storage, or distribution systems. Total coliforms are widely used as indicators of water quality because they reflect environmental contamination and the sanitary integrity of water systems. Their detection in drinking water contravenes recommended standards, as potable water should ideally be free from such organisms (WHO, 2017). The present study assessed the level of parasitological and microbiological contamination in water samples obtained from different sources, including

borehole, rainwater, municipal water, itinerant water supply, sachet water, and bottled water. The findings revealed that 27 samples were contaminated with parasites, while 47 samples were contaminated with microorganisms, indicating a substantial burden of water contamination across all sources. Borehole water, often considered a relatively safe source of drinking water in many developing regions, showed notable contamination, with 7 samples containing parasites and 12 contaminated with microorganisms. This finding suggests that groundwater sources are vulnerable to contamination, particularly in areas with poor sanitation, improper waste disposal, and shallow construction. Similar studies have reported the presence of both parasitic and bacterial contaminants in borehole water due to infiltration of faecal matter and environmental pollutants (Bergwerff and Debast, 2021; WHO, 2017). Rainwater samples showed comparatively lower contamination, with 2 samples containing parasites and 5 contaminated with microorganisms. Although rainwater is generally perceived as clean, contamination can occur during collection and storage, especially when harvested from dry rooftops or stored in unclean containers. Previous studies have indicated that rainwater can harbor microbial pathogens introduced from atmospheric deposition, animal droppings, and debris on catchment surface. Municipal water sources recorded relatively high contamination levels, with 7 samples containing parasites and 12 contaminated with microorganisms. This is of particular concern, as municipal water is expected to undergo treatment before distribution. The presence of contaminants suggests possible inefficiencies in treatment processes or post-treatment contamination within distribution systems. Similar observations have been reported in developing countries, where aging infrastructure, intermittent supply, and pipe leakages contribute to microbial contamination of treated water (WHO, 2017).

The relationship between hygiene practices and water contamination was clearly demonstrated in this study. Vendors were categorized based on their hygiene practices as good, moderate, and poor. Among the 15 vendors who practiced good hygiene, 14 contaminated water samples were recorded. In contrast, 20 vendors with moderate hygiene practices accounted for 24 contaminated samples, while 25 vendors with poor hygiene practices contributed the highest number of contaminated samples (36). This trend indicates a strong association between the level of hygiene practice and the degree of water contamination. Although contamination was observed even among vendors with good hygiene practices, the relatively lower number of contaminated samples compared to other categories suggests that proper hygiene significantly reduces, but does not completely eliminate, the risk of contamination. This residual

contamination may be attributed to factors beyond the control of vendors, such as contamination at the source, poor water quality before collection, or environmental exposure during transportation and storage (WHO, 2017). Similar findings have been reported in previous studies, where even treated or carefully handled water could become contaminated due to external environmental factors (Cudjoe *et.al.*, 2022). The increase in contamination among vendors with moderate hygiene practices (24 samples) highlights the impact of inconsistent or partially implemented sanitary measures. Moderate hygiene may include irregular cleaning of containers, inadequate hand washing, or improper covering of water storage vessels. These lapses create opportunities for microbial introduction and proliferation. Studies have shown that improper handling and storage of water significantly contribute to post-treatment contamination, especially in low-resource settings (Lee and Seo, 2020). The highest contamination level observed among vendors practicing poor hygiene (36 samples) further reinforces the critical role of sanitation in water safety. Poor hygiene practices, such as the use of unclean containers, lack of hand hygiene, exposure of water to open environments, and repeated dipping of utensils into storage vessels, are well-documented pathways for parasitic or microbial contamination. Such practices facilitate the introduction of pathogens from human, animal, and environmental sources into water intended for consumption or food preparation (Jevsnik and Raspor, 2022). These results are in line with earlier research demonstrating that hygiene behaviour is a key determinant of water quality at the point of use. Even when water is sourced from relatively safe supplies, contamination can occur during handling, storage, and distribution. This phenomenon, often referred to as “secondary contamination,” has been widely reported in developing countries and is a major contributor to waterborne diseases (WHO, 2017; Lee and Seo, 2020).

CONCLUSION:

The result of the study show serious concerns about the parasitological and microbiological quality of water samples and the effect of hygiene practices on contamination rates. Besides, there is a clear relationship between hygiene practices and contamination rates that have been confirmed through this study. The results of this study emphasize the need for better water treatment and sanitation procedures.

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The authors received no external funding for this study.

Conflict of Interest:

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this article.

Data Availability Statement

Data Availability Statement:

The datasets generated and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Limitations:

- The study was limited to selected restaurants and local food vendors within Aba metropolis and may not represent all food establishments in Abia State.
- Seasonal variations in water quality were not evaluated.
- Viral contaminants were not investigated.
- Molecular techniques were not employed for confirmation of microbial and parasitic isolates.
- The findings were based on a cross-sectional assessment and therefore cannot establish temporal changes in contamination levels.

Author Contributions:

John OG conceived and designed the study. All authors participated in sample collection, laboratory analysis, data interpretation, manuscript preparation, and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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